

Market-Clearing and Pricing of Required Ancillary Services for Improvement in Frequency Stability of Power Grids with High Penetration of Renewable Energy Sources

Mohammad Rayati and Mohammadreza Toulabi

In this document, we provide the proof of two propositions used in the main manuscript.

APPENDIX A-PROOF OF PROPOSITION 1

The dynamic of power grid frequency can be written as a differential equation (S-1).

$$M_h^{eq} \frac{df_{th}}{dt} = R_h^{eq} t - D_h(f_{th} - 1) - G_h, \quad (\text{S-1})$$

in which,

t Index of time step;
 f_{th} Frequency at time step t at hour h in per-unit.

Using the Laplace transform and inverse Laplace transform, f_{th} is computed as follows:

$$f_{th} = 1 - \left(\frac{D_h G_h + M_h^{eq} R_h^{eq}}{(D_h)^2} \right) \left(\exp\left(\frac{-D_h t}{M_h^{eq}}\right) - 1 \right) - \frac{R_h^{eq}}{D_h} t. \quad (\text{S-2})$$

Using the derivative of (S-2), $|RoCoF_h|$ and f_h^{nad} are computed as follows:

$$|RoCoF_h| = \frac{G_h}{M_h^{eq}}, \quad \forall h \in \mathbb{H}, \quad (\text{S-3a})$$

$$f_h^{nad} = 1 - \frac{M_h^{eq} R_h^{eq}}{(D_h)^2} \ln \left(\frac{1}{\frac{D_h G_h}{M_h^{eq} R_h^{eq}} + 1} \right) - \frac{G_h}{D_h}, \quad \forall h \in \mathbb{H}. \quad (\text{S-3b})$$

□

APPENDIX B-PROOF OF PROPOSITION 2

The function of left-hand side of (8a) with respect to $M_h^{eq} R_h^{eq}$ is as follows:

$$F(x) = -x \ln \left(\frac{1}{\frac{b}{x} + 1} \right)$$

The derivative of this function is as follows:

$$\frac{\partial F(x)}{\partial x} = -\ln \left(\frac{1}{\frac{b}{x} + 1} \right) + \frac{1}{\frac{b}{x} + 1} - 1$$

By replacing $1/(b/x + 1)$ with y , if we prove:

$$-\ln(y) + y - 1 > 0, \quad \forall 0 < y < 1,$$

then, we prove that function $F(x)$ is strongly increasing and one-to-one. The positiveness of $-\ln(y) + y - 1$ for $y \in (0, 1)$ can be easily shown. □